

Study of Cu, Fe and Zn removal using Key Lime leaves (*Citrus aurentifolia*) as low cost adsorbent

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Abstract : Biosorption of Cu^{2+} , Fe^{2+} and Zn^{2+} from synthetically prepared waste water was studied using low cost adsorbent, Key Lime leaves. In the present study various biosorption parameters such as contact time, adsorbent dose, pH, concentration of metal ions and temperature have been used. Maximum biosorption efficiency achieved at high pH, high dose of adsorbent and low initial concentration of metal ions. The biosorption efficiency recorded for Cu^{2+} , Fe^{2+} and Zn^{2+} at pH 5 is 77.57, 80.82 and 56.97 respectively after 25 min at 170 rpm. The equilibrium adsorption data were best fitted to Langmuir, Freundlich and Temkin isotherm model and model parameters were evaluated. A high regression value (R^2) and other parameters indicate favorable adsorption of Cu^{2+} , Fe^{2+} and Zn^{2+} on to Key Lime leaves.

Keywords : Biosorption, heavy metals, lime leave, isotherm model.

Introduction

Biosorption, which means sorption onto biomaterials or nonliving microorganisms, has emerged as one of the most promising technique. It can be an alternative to the usual treatments of waste water aimed at reducing the metal concentrations under the levels established by the legislation¹. These heavy metals are particularly hazardous and often detrimental to health. Various methods cited in the literature for the removal of heavy metals from water and waste water are chemical precipitation, membrane filtration, ion exchange, carbon adsorption and biosorption. Among these biosorption is relatively new and cost effective method for the removal of heavy metals. Many reports have appeared on the development of low cost adsorbents prepared from cheaper and easily available materials². Key Lime leaves are easily available in the Kumaun hills of India. Therefore these leaves can be used as an effective adsorbent for the removal of heavy metal ions Cu^{2+} , Fe^{2+} and Zn^{2+} from industrial waste water. Copper is found in sizeable amounts in liquid effluent streams of printed circuit board plants, tanning, insecticides and fungicides. Hyper accumulation of cop-

per in human body causes liver damage, chronic poisoning and gastrointestinal catarrh. Iron exists in two forms ferrous (soluble) and ferric (insoluble) form. The presence of iron in natural water may be due to the dissolution of rocks and minerals, acid mine drainage, land fill leachate, sewage or engineering industries. Iron over load may cause to debilitating and life threatening problems such as diabetes, heart failure and poor growth³. Zinc is the most common pollutant which arises from industries such as electroplating, mineral processing, galvanizing plants, paint formulation, porcelain enameling, and vegetable fat producing industries. Abdominal pain, lack of muscular coordination and acute renal failure are some of the complications of zinc.

Results and discussion

Effect of contact time :

The removal of copper, iron and zinc from synthetic waste water increases with increasing contact time. But in case of iron, removal attains equilibrium after 60 min. It may be due to the factor that, the less availability of active sites on adsorbent after this contact time^{1,5}. The

removal efficiency achieved 27.71 for Cu^{2+} , 63.95 for Fe^{2+} and 13.68 for Zn^{2+} after 75 min at pH 3 and concentration 10 mg/L (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Effect of contact time on removal of copper, iron and zinc.

Dosage effect of adsorbent :

The dependence of copper, iron and zinc removal on adsorbent dose was studied by varying the amounts of adsorbent 0.25 to 1.0 g while keeping other parameters pH, concentration, and contact time constant. It can be inferred that the percentage removal of these metal ion increases with adsorbent dose. Fig. 2. shows that with adsorbent dose of 1 g there is an increase in the percentage removal. The larger the surface area, larger the amount of metal ion adsorbed. This may be due to the increase in available binding sites in the adsorbent for complexation of heavy metal ions⁶. The adsorbent is able to achieve the percentage removal of 33.94, 66.93 and 13.23 for Cu^{2+} , Fe^{2+} and Zn^{2+} at pH 3 and at concentration 10 mg/L.

Fig. 2. Effect of dosage of adsorbent on removal of copper, iron and zinc.

Effect of pH :

The effect of pH on the removal of copper, iron and zinc is represented in Fig. 3. At low pH, the synthetic waste water is highly protonated and the active sites on adsorbent becomes positively charged^{5,7}. This results in repulsion between metal ions and adsorbent and thus decreases biosorption efficiency of adsorbent. The high pH makes the adsorbent less protonated and so the metal removal efficiency increases. Maximum removal efficiency achieved at pH 5 is 77.57 for copper, 80.82 for iron and 56.97 for zinc.

Fig. 3. Effect of pH on removal of copper, iron and zinc.

Effect of initial concentration of metal ions :

Fig. 4, shows that the percentage removal of Cu^{2+} , Fe^{2+} and Zn^{2+} decreases with increasing concentration of metal ions in solution. The maximum biosorption efficiency is obtained at concentration 10 mg/L of synthetic waste water but the amount of metal adsorbed per unit

Fig. 4. Effect of initial metal ion concentrations on removal of copper, iron and zinc.

mass of adsorbent (mg/g) increases with concentration.

Effect of temperature :

As shown in Fig. 5, the removal efficiency decreases after 30 °C. In Cu²⁺ the maximum percentage removal achieved at 30 °C is 25.90. It decreases to 21.60 at 75 °C. For Fe²⁺ maximum removal achieved 48.48 at 30 °C and for Zn²⁺ it is 14.93 at 60 °C. So these experimental data indicate that the removal decreases after certain temperature, it may be attributed to solubility of metal ions from adsorbent in solution with rise of temperature^{9,10}.

Fig. 5. Effect of temperature on removal of copper, iron and zinc.

Adsorption isotherms :

The Langmuir, Freundlich and Temkin isotherm model have been applied for copper, iron and zinc adsorption onto Key Lime leaves. Langmuir isotherm¹¹ assumes monolayer adsorption onto a surface containing a finite number of adsorption sites of uniform strategies of adsorption with no transmigration of adsorbate in the plane of surface. The linear form of Langmuir isotherm equation is given as :

$$C_e/q_e = 1/K_L b + 1/K_L C_e \quad (1)$$

where q_e is the amount of adsorbate adsorbed per unit mass of adsorbent (mg/g). K_L and b are Langmuir constants related to adsorption capacity and rate of adsorption respectively. When C_e/q_e was plotted against C_e , a straight line with slope of $1/K_L$ was obtained (Fig. 6). The essential characteristic of the Langmuir isotherm can be expressed in terms of dimensionless equilibrium parameter (R_L) which is defined as $R_L = 1/1 + bC_0$ where

Fig. 6. Langmuir isotherm model for copper, iron and zinc on Key Lime leaves.

b is the Langmuir constant and C_0 is the initial metal ion concentration (mg/L). The value of R_L indicates type of isotherm to be either favorable ($0 < R_L < 1$), unfavorable ($R_L > 1$), linear ($R_L = 1$) or irreversible ($R_L = 0$). The value of R_L was found to be less than one in all cases reported here and this confirms that the Langmuir isotherm model is favorable for adsorption of Cu²⁺, Fe²⁺ and Zn²⁺ on to Key Lime leaf powder. Iron shows more adsorption capacity (K_L) than copper and zinc whereas the rate of adsorption (b) of copper is more than iron and zinc (Table 1).

Table 1. Langmuir adsorption constant for copper, iron and zinc onto Key Lime leaves

Metal	K_L	b	R^2
Cu	5.659	0.301	0.971
Fe	9.852	0.0638	0.926
Zn	5.330	0.0752	0.991

Freundlich isotherm¹² is an empirical expression based on biosorption on a heterogenous surface. The linear form of Freundlich equation is given by the following expression :

$$\log q_e = \log K_F + 1/n \log C_e \quad (2)$$

where q_e is the amount of metal ions adsorbed per gram weight of adsorbent at equilibrium (mg/g) and C_e represents the equilibrium concentration of adsorbate (mg/L). K_F and n are Freundlich constants representing the adsorption capacity and intensity of adsorption respectively. The value of K and $1/n$ were obtained from the slope and intercept of the plot, $\log q_e$ versus $\log C_e$ (Fig. 7). The regression value (R^2) show that iron favors multilayer

Fig. 7. Freundlich isotherm model for copper, iron and zinc on Key Lime leaves.

adsorption on a heterogenous surface of Key Lime leaf powder more than zinc and copper (Table 2). In this pattern iron shows more adsorption capacity (K_F), 1.150 than copper and zinc. The value of $1/n$ is less than one in all cases, which also favors Freundlich isotherm model.

Table 2. Freundlich adsorption constant for copper, iron and zinc onto Key Lime leaves

Metal	K_F	$1/n$	R^2
Cu	0.3041	0.634	0.961
Fe	1.150	0.456	0.975
Zn	0.731	0.459	0.966

Temkin isotherm model considers the effect of indirect adsorbate-adsorbate interaction which explains that the heat of adsorption of all the molecules on the adsorbent surface would decrease linearly with coverage due to adsorbate-adsorbate interaction¹³. Therefore the adsorption potentials of the adsorbent for the adsorbate can be evaluated using Temkin isotherm model, which assumes that the fall in heat of sorption is linear rather than logarithmic as implied in the Freundlich equation. The Temkin isotherm model is given by the following equation :

$$q_e = a + b \ln C_e \quad (3)$$

where C_e is the equilibrium concentration of metal ions in mg/L, q_e is the amount of adsorbate in mg/g, a and b are constants related to adsorption capacity and intensity of adsorption. The value of a and b can be determined by plot (Fig. 8) of q_e versus $\ln C_e$. In this pattern iron shows more adsorption capacity 1.925 as well as adsorption intensity 2.258 than copper and zinc (Table 3).

Fig. 8. Temkin isotherm model for copper, iron and zinc on Key Lime leaves.

Table 3. Temkin adsorption constant for copper, iron and zinc onto Key Lime leaf powder

Metal	a	b	R^2
Cu	1.629	1.277	0.935
Fe	1.925	2.258	0.935
Zn	0.923	1.318	0.980

Experimental

Chemicals :

All the chemicals from commercial sources were of the highest available purity and we used double distilled water to prepare all solutions.

Preparation of adsorbent :

The collected waste leaves were washed several times with distilled water to remove the surface adhered particles and water soluble impurities. The leaves were dried for 5-6 days in laboratory and then heated at 70 °C for 3 h in an oven. The dried adsorbent was crushed and sieved to particle size 63 microns for uniform size.

Preparation of synthetic waste water :

The synthetic waste water containing Cu^{2+} , Fe^{2+} and Zn^{2+} were separately prepared from their salts ($\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{FeSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{ZnSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$) in double distilled water. For making 1000 mg/L of Cu^{2+} , Fe^{2+} and Zn^{2+} , 3.921 g of $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 4.978 g of $\text{FeSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and 4.397 g of $\text{ZnSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ were added separately in 1000 ml of double distilled water. The pH of the solution was adjusted 3 by digital pH meter (Model : MAC 12831). These solutions were used to prepare other dilute solutions.

Adsorption study :

Adsorption study was carried out by batch operation in different process conditions such as contact time, dosage effect of adsorbent, pH and initial concentration of metal ions. A 100 ml solution containing requisite amount of Cu²⁺, Fe²⁺ and Zn²⁺ was treated with 1 g of adsorbent in a conical flask at a constant rpm 170. The concentration of these metal ions before and after adsorption was determined by Atomic Absorption spectrophotometer (Model : AAS vario 6, analytik Jena, Germany). The biosorption efficiency of heavy metal ions was calculated by using the following formula :

$$\text{Biosorption efficiency} = \frac{C_0 - C_e}{C_0} \times 100$$

where C₀ is the initial metal ion concentration (mg/L) and C_e is the equilibrium metal ion concentration (mg/L).

Conclusion :

This work attempts to explore the potential use of *Citrus aurentifolia* biomass as a low cost adsorbent for the effective removal of copper, iron and zinc. Batch experiments show that Key Lime leaves have remarkable ability to take up copper, iron and zinc heavy metal ions from synthetic waste water. A high correlation is represented for Langmuir, Freundlich and Temkin isotherm model. The adsorption capacity is found by Langmuir model for copper, iron and zinc onto Key Lime leave powder in the order of Fe > Zn > Cu.

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